

Challenging Discontinuities in Early Years Math Pedagogy: a participatory, cross-sectoral approach to improving math outcomes for lower SES children in Ireland

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Research findings point to strong links between socioeconomic disadvantage and educational outcomes in mathematics. This paper presents an overview of some of the literature and the methodology underpinning the ‘Count Me In’ project which aims to improve mathematics outcomes and pedagogical discontinuities for children experiencing socioeconomic disadvantage through establishing cross-sectoral professional learning communities made up of educators from pre compulsory and compulsory school sectors. Early findings from the project suggest that while participatory methods are complex and messy, they provide scope for improved teacher agency, create a forum for depersonalised collective enquiry, foster the use of evidence-aware practices in math, and address transition discontinuities via a focus on math pedagogy.

Keywords: early mathematics education, socioeconomic disadvantage, cross curricular collaboration, transition, participatory research

Theoretical Perspective

There is a strong link between socioeconomic disadvantage and educational outcomes in mathematics. In Ireland, at primary school level, there have been attempts to mitigate this negative relationship, primarily through the DEIS Scheme (Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools). Whilst the scheme has seen some improvement in student outcomes in mathematics, the 2018 PISA report highlights that Irish pupils from non DEIS schools continue to ‘significantly and substantially’ outperform those from DEIS schools in math, with students from non DEIS schools performing above the OECD average and those from DEIS schools scoring significantly below it (OECD, 2019). While the reasons for this are complex and, notwithstanding structural injustices, schools are institutions that can be seen to maintain existing cycles of advantage and disadvantage rather than acting to disrupt them. Several studies have shown that well-planned mathematical programmes in early education settings can work toward reducing the achievement gap between lower SES children and more middle SES groups (e.g. Anthony and Walshaw, 2009).

The transition from pre-school to primary school is increasingly seen as a dynamic process of continuity and change (ETC, 2011) rather than an event reliant on maturational constructs of preparedness (Boyle, Petriwskyj and Grieshaber, 2018). Internationally, research suggests that children from lower socio-economic backgrounds are on average more likely to experience difficult transitions to school, stemming in part from curriculum and pedagogical discontinuity and lack of practice sharing.

Maths in Early Childhood

International research consistently points to the need for high expectations of young children’s potential as learners of mathematics where effective math pedagogy is built on the premise that all students are powerful mathematics learners (Anthony and Walshaw, 2009). With the advent of neuroscience relating to mathematics learning, there is a growing

awareness that mathematics is for all and that young children can access powerful mathematical ideas regardless of age or background (Perry and Dockett, 2008).

Communities of Practice

A common theme across much of the literature around effective early years practice is that of partnerships: partnerships between educators and families, educators and the community, educators, and children and increasingly, between educators themselves. It has been argued that to better understand the effective pedagogies and practices that enhance young children's learning in math, more cross sectoral research is needed (c.f. Anthony and Walshaw, 2009, Perry and Dockett, 2008). Communities of practice can act as a framework within which collective reasoning, linking lived and formal experience, and mobilising for future practice can take place (Boonstra et al., 2022) in order to improve practices and bring about sustainable, context driven change.

Methodology

This study adopts a critical participatory action research approach that builds on Habermas' notion of the public sphere (Habermas, 1992) and views research as a social practice (Kemmis et al., 2014). It arises as a critique of conventional research in acknowledging that research is a social practice that can challenge what is unproductive, irrational, and unjust in our collective practice. This collaborative approach to research values shared ownership, seeks a community-based analysis of problems and subsequent action is community orientated.

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